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Influence of Parental Guidance and Socioeconomic Status on Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards Sexual Behaviour in Edo and Delta States

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of parental guidance and socioeconomic status on Upper Basic Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The study was premised on the fact that parental guidance and socio-economic status are capable of influencing students' sexual behaviour at the Upper Basic level in both states. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was Fifty-one thousand, six hundred and twenty-four. The sample size for the study was 720 respondents arrived at using the multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Data generated were analyzed using the simple correlation statistics for the research questions while the Simple Regression was used to test the formulated null hypotheses at an alpha of 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that, there was a significant relationship between parental guidance and socio-economic status on Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in the area under review. The study concluded that parental guidance and socio-economic status influences Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The study recommended that enlightenment on safe behavioural approach to sex and sexual outcomes amongst Upper Basic Social Studies students to forestall unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases should be routinely conducted.

KEYWORDS:

Parental Guidance, Socio-economic Status, Social Studies, Sexual Behaviour.

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Introduction

Sex so small a word, yet is an explosive subject which people desperately want answers to related problems. Knowledge and attitude about sex is so vital that people (students) seek it from whatever sources that are available, good or bad. When accurate information is not available, students will ignorantly accept misinformation for truth. This is especially noticeable among adolescents. Adolescence is a period of transition between childhood and adulthood. It occupies a crucial and important place in the life of human beings whereby transition is characterized by rapid rate of growth. The origin of the term which is from the Latin word, “adolescere” meaning “to grow, to mature” indicate the defining features of adolescence (Maan, Yadav & Chaudhary, 2021). However, a universally accepted definition of the concept has not been established. World Health Organization (2017) sees adolescence both in terms of the age (spanning the ages between 10 and 19 years) and in terms of a phase of life marked by special attributes. These attributes which is related to their sexual behaviour encompasses rapid physical growth and development; physical, social and psychological maturity, but not all at the same time; sexual maturity and the onset of sexual activity; experimentation; development of adult mental process and adult identity; transition from total dependence to relative independence as a result of characteristics inherent in the society (Maan et al., 2021). These characteristics tend to influence their attitudes towards sexual behaviour within and outside the school setting.

Sexual behaviour of students in recent times has become very problematic. Coital and premarital sex among Nigeria students are on the increase. It appears present day school children, Social Studies students inclusive value sexual activities more compared to their mates of the old; which invariably leads to complications amongst adolescents in the society if not managed appropriately. Samuel and Sanusi (2019) stressed that more than one million adolescents become pregnant with sixty-five percent of them having babies out of wedlock; giving credence to the fact that students sexual behaviour needs to be checked. In the same vein, Nigussie, Legese, Abebe, Getachew and Alemayehu (2020) ascertained that between 2.5 and 5 million adolescents acquire sexually transmitted diseases each year as a result of sexual behaviour which to a large extent can be attributed to the development and advancement of the society.

Parental guidance ensures that students are observed, groomed and indoctrinated properly to prevent them from straying negatively, especially in the aspect of sexual behaviour which is very prevalent in the society. Parental guidance in the view of Oluyemi, Yinusa, Abdullateef, Kehinde and Adejoke (2017) helps to find solutions to inherent problems such as sexual behaviour in the adolescent with particular focus to instilling discipline in their wards/students (children). Emphasis on their study was laid on frequent communication between parents and their child/children with a view to instilling morals that cannot be compromised by societal and peer pressures if not monitored. A positive parent-child communication is capable of setting a stray child aright.

In the view of Muthengi and Ferede (2016), Positive parent-child communication can help young people to establish individual values and make healthy decisions. Their studies show that young people who feel a lack of parental warmth, love or care are more likely to report emotional distress, school problems, drug use and sexual risk behaviours. Parent-child communication regarding sex has many positive effects for adolescent, including better contraception use and healthier sexual behaviours. A large number of studies, mainly from developed countries, have examined the effect of parental communication on adolescent sexual behaviour. In the southwest United States of America, adolescents who had a healthy discussion with parents in the last year about sex, birth control and the

dangers of sexually transmitted infections were significantly more likely to use condoms the last time they had sex than adolescents who did not talk to their parents as often (Muthengi & Ferede, 2016).

Debele, Tsegaye, Gemechu and Siraj (2022) observed that parental monitoring is the better way of mitigating risky sexual behaviour of students as it limits their exposure to a variety of sexual and reproductive health problems. They noted that monitoring of wards' activities can help evade the dangers associated with unchecked sexual fantasies in the society. It is pertinent to note that in monitoring of students' sexual behaviour, parents should also be equipped with the means to do so as anything short of this will result in their wards ignoring their views. Emphasis here is placed on the economic status of parents; as it is a key aspect in monitoring of children. The socio-economic status of parents plays a large role in monitoring and curtailing activities of a child in that, such a child from a sound socio-economic background cannot be influence and enticed to engage in sexual act easily, hence, the strength of socio-economic status of parents in wading off risky sexual behaviour of Social Studies students.

Socio-economic status of parents entails the financial standing in the society. This is capable of influencing Social Studies students' sexual behaviour. Also, a parents' socio-economic status will determine many things about a child's early development: how he/she views the world and interact with peer; what, how much, and how often he eat; the type of Early Childhood Education he receive; his or her overall health; or how others view him or her. It also impacts a child's later success or failure in life. Thus, there is need for this variable to be factored into a child schooling, especially when it has to do with sexual behaviour.

In the view of Berhan and Berhan (2015) issue of socio-economic status of parents do influence a child to engage in sex without using any form of protection, having multiple sexual partners, early sexual debut, and transactional sex or engaging in any behaviour that puts an individual at risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases. It could be deduced from their view that the level of socio-economic status of parents does influence a child to engage in or not in sexual behaviour within and outside the school. The consequences of this include, but are not limited to HIV/AIDS, unwanted pregnancy, and unsafe abortions. Even though trends suggest an increase in condom use over the past years, adolescents and young adults, Social Studies students inclusive continue to engage in unprotected sex (Torrone et al., 2018) and a high proportion of the HIV infections in Nigerian compared to other developed regions (WHO, 2018). The implication here is that the level of socio-economic status of parent do have a multiplying effect on their wards with regards to accepting or not of moral dictates that restrain them from engaging in sexual behaviour that can best be describe as detrimental; and can best be attributed to peer pressure (USAID, 2018). This is so because they feel left out when they are not engaged in sexual act in the school and belonging to a clique engaging in it, giving credence to the sway of peer in sexual indulgence by students.

The trend of adolescent sexual behaviours has attracted a plethora of stakeholders in Nigeria. The various people concerned have been involved in curbing these sexual behaviours among the adolescents/students in Nigeria through various campaigns with slogans such as "sex is worth waiting for, Zip up" among others. Some others have organized workshops and seminars, but these seem to be yielding very little results; hence, the need to properly examine the influence of parental guidance and socio-economic status on Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Statement of the Problem

The present day school system is gradually transforming from an academic environment to an institution of promiscuity, moral laxity as well as sexual permissiveness. The reason for this

behaviour is not farfetched. The glamorization of sex and suggestive sexual scene in the media, permissive attitude of some parents and economic standing of families with regards to their desire to belong and survive, amongst others may account for bad sexual behaviour. It was observed that the parental guidance and socio-economic status, are variables to be studied in this study as they do have the tendency to influence students towards varied sexual behaviour with students as victim of unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases as a result of unpleasant sexual activities. There is therefore, the need to investigate the pertinent question here which is: To what extent would parental guidance and socio-economic status influence Upper Basic Social Studies students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- i. What is the relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?
- ii. What is the relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies student' towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

- i. There is no significant relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies student' towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all Upper Basic II Social Studies Students in Edo and Delta States public secondary schools; succinctly put at 51, 624. The multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select 720 respondents as the sample size for the study. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument obtained a reliability index of 0.793; making it reliable for use for this study. The collated data were analyzed using the simple correlation and the simple regression (ANOVA) for the research questions and formulated null hypotheses at an alpha of 0.05 level of significance. This was done to establish relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable of the study.

Results

Research Questions 1: What is the relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta State?

Table 1: Simple Correlation Analysis of Parental Guidance and Social Studies students Sexual Behaviour

Variables	N	r	r ²	r ^{2adj}
Parental guidance				
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.029	.001	-.001

Independent Variable: Parental Guidance, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour.

Table 1 presents the simple correlation results. It revealed that parental guidance as indicated by r -value of .029 shows a positive relationship between parental guidance and Social Studies students' sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 1. It revealed that there is a positive relationship between parental guidance and Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r^2 adjusted value of -.001 indicates that parental guidance can impact students' sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. In order to test hypothesis 1, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between Parental Guidance and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean (x̄) Score	F	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	11.807	1	11.807	.615	-.784	.027	.43
Residual	13584.617	719	19.187				
Total	13596.424	720					

$P \geq 0.05$ level of significance; $N = 720$

As shown in Table 2, the computed ANOVA produced an $F = .615$, $P \geq 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between parental guidance and Upper basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour was accepted. The finding is that there is no significant relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The conclusion is reached that parental guidance has positive contribution to sexual behaviour of students involved in this study.

Research Questions 2: What is the relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States?

Table 3: Simple Correlation Analysis of Socio-Economic Status and Social Studies Students sexual behaviour

Variables	N	r	r^2	r^{2adj}
Socio-Economic Status				
Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour	720	.087	.008	.006

Independent Variable: Socio-Economic Status, Dependent Variable: Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour.

Table 3 presents the simple correlation results where it revealed that socio-economic status as indicated by r -value of .087 showed a positive relationship between socio-economic status and Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. This provides an answer to research question 2. It revealed that there is a positive relationship between socioeconomic status and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The r^2 adjusted value of .006 indicated that socioeconomic status has impact on Social Studies students' sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between socio-economic status and Upper basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. In order to test hypothesis 2, simple regression was computed. The summary of the output is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis of the relationship between Socio-Economic Status and Social Studies Students Sexual Behaviour

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean ($\bar{x}$) Score	F	t	Std Error	Sig
Regression	103.882	1	103.882	5.451	-2.33	.034	.02
Residual	13492.541	719	19.057				
Total	13596.424	720					

$P \leq 0.05$ level of significance; $N = 720$

As shown in Table 4 the computed ANOVA produced an $F = .5.451$, $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour was rejected. The finding was that there is a significant relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies students towards sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States. The conclusion is reached that socio-economic status of students has positive contribution to their sexual behaviour in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis one, it was revealed that there was a significant relationship between parental guidance and Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour. This finding is at variance with the study by Debele, Tsegaye, Gemechu and Siraj (2022) who found that sexual activities is significantly decreased when the parental and family monitoring is put in place. This shows that parental and family guidance does influence students' sexual behaviour. Also, the study by Ojo, Makinde and Obiyan (2021) agreed with the findings of this current study where they observed that mothers and fathers do have influence on students' indulgence in sexual behaviour, where their findings received a total of 57% of the total responses with regards to parental influence on students' indulgence in sexual activities. The implication here is that parental guidance does have influence on students' sexual behaviour in secondary school. It was also discovered that the main source of influence of students' socialization for many young people are their parents or guardians (Mmari, Sommer, Kabiru, Fatusi, Bello, Adepoju and Maina, 2017), giving credence to the strength of parents in students sexual behaviour. The findings from this study also disagree with the study conducted by Oluyemi, Yinusa, Abdullateef, Kehinde and Adejoke (2017) that showed a positive relationship between parental monitoring and participants' sexual behaviour. Their study suggested that parental supervision and control on adolescents affects adolescents' tendency of being involved in sex till a later date when they are more matured to handle it. Their study also confirmed a significant relationship between parental supervision and monitoring with regards to family rules, household routines, parental supervision in dating activities with adolescents not having sexual intercourse till a later date or having fewer sexual partners.

Result from hypothesis two showed that there was a significant relationship between socio-economic status and Upper Basic Social Studies Students towards sexual behaviour. This finding showed that socio-economic status of students does have a bearing on the way they display their sexual fantasy. This study support the findings of De Looze, Constantine, Jerman, Vermeulen-Smit

and ter Bogt (2015) who observed that lower levels of socio-economic status (SES) are associated with a lower age of sexual behaviour/debut and higher levels of SES with a higher age of sexual behaviour/debut SES and students sexual behaviour and that they seem to be associated; they noted that higher levels of SES seem to be positively associated with more successful students sexual behaviour practices, and lower levels of SES with less successful ones. In the same vein, the current study is also in agreement with the work of Abar, Clark and Koban (2017) who found that economic hardship might result in a change in behavioural and emotional functioning of students, foremost causing problems in the relationship between the students, as well as changes in the behaviour, that are disproportionately harsh and inconsistent at least.

This study is also in agreement with the study by the UNAIDS (2019), where they found that poverty increases vulnerability to sexual promiscuity for the adolescent with the attendant consequences of contracting STI, HIV/AIDS, getting pregnant, abortions, engaging in risky sexual behaviour, amongst others. The UNAIDS noted that these burden is concentrated in the poorest regions of the world, and the prevalence among people (students) living in slums is high compared with that of people in other formal urban settlements; giving credence to the influence of socio-economic variable as an indices in sexual behaviour of students, Social Studies students inclusive.

Conclusion

Sexual behaviour in adolescence is inevitable as it is a developmental task. Its orientation includes physiological, psychological and sociological influences. In this investigation, it was demonstrated that students' sexual behaviour is influenced by parental guidance and socio-economic status. Chiefly, the study concluded that:

- i. Parental guidance does influence Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.
- ii. Socio-economic status influence Upper Basic Social Studies Students sexual behaviour in Edo and Delta States.

Recommendations

Following from the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Enlightenment on safe behavioural approach to sex and sexual outcomes among Upper Basic Social Studies students to forestall unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted disease should be routinely conducted
- ii. The influence of parents and peer influence need to be given priority attention when adolescents' sexual behaviour discussions are held in Nigeria. Parents also should increase their communication with their adolescents especially on sex and sex related issues in order for adolescents to be adequately informed.

References

- Abar, C. C., Clark, G., & Koban, K. (2017). The long-term impact of family routines and parental knowledge on alcohol use and health behaviours: results from a 14 year follow-up. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 26(9), 2495-2504.
- Berhan, Y. & Berhan, A. (2015). A meta-analysis of risky sexual behaviour among male youth in developing countries. *AIDS Research and Treatment*, 580961. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/580961>
- De Looze, M., Constantine, N. A., Jerman, P., Vermeulen-Smit, E., & ter Bogt, T. (2015). Parent-adolescent sexual communication and its association with adolescent sexual behaviours: A nationally representative analysis in the Netherlands. *The Journal of Sex Research*, 52(3), 257-268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2013.858307>
- Debele, G. R., Tsegaye, D., Gemechu, T & Siraj, S. Z. (2022). Influences of parental monitoring and school connectedness on age at first sexual debut among unmarried female youth in Bedele town, Ethiopia: A survival analysis of timing using accelerated failure time model. *PLoS ONE* 17(7), e0271906. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271906>
- Maan, A., Yadav, M. K. & Chaudhary, S. S. (2021). A study on sexual behaviour practiced by the adolescent and its source of inspiration. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 8(4), 1911-1916. Retrieved 13th February, 2023 from <http://www.ijcmph.com>
- Mmari, K., Sommer, M., Kabiru, C. W., Fatusi, A. O., Bello, B. M., Adepoju, O. E., & Maina, B. W. (2017). Adolescent and Parental Reactions to Puberty in Nigeria and Kenya: A Cross-Cultural and Intergenerational Comparison. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 61(4), S35-S41.
- Muthengi, E. & Ferede, A. (2016). Effects of parent-child communication regarding sexuality, family planning and HIV on reproductive health outcomes among unmarried adolescent girls in rural Tanzania. Population Council, Nairobi, Kenya and Population Council, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia
- Nigussie T, Legese T, Abebe L, Getachew S. & Alemayehu D. (2020). Magnitude of risky sexual behaviours, determinants, and consequences among high school and preparatory school students in Mizan Aman Town, Ethiopia. *Journal of Midwifery and Reproductive Health*. 8(1), 2096-2104. DOI: 10.22038/jmrh.2019.40248.1450
- Ojo, T. O., Makinde, O. N. & Obiyan, M. O. (2021). Parental factors and sexual health profile of students in public tertiary institutions in Osun State. *Ife Social Sciences Review* 29(1), 81-91
- Oluyemi, J. A., Yinusa, M. A., Abdullateef, R., Kehinde, K. & Adejoke, J. (2017). parental influence on adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Ogbomosho, Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Work*, 7(1), 37-43
- Samuel, B. O. & Sanusi, R. A. (2019). Sexual behaviours and experience of sexual coercion among in-school female adolescent in southwestern Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.1101/19000851>

Torrone, E. A., Morrison, C. S., Chen, P. L., Kwok, C., Francis, S. C., Hayes, R. J. & STIMA Working Group. (2018). Prevalence of sexually transmitted infections and bacterial vaginosis among women in sub-Saharan Africa: An individual participant data meta-analysis of 18 HIV prevention studies. *PLoS Medicine*, 15(2), e1002511. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1002511

UNAIDS (2018). At a glance. Retrieved from <http://www.unaids.org>

World Health Organisation (WHO) (2017). *Expanding access to contraceptive services for adolescents*. Geneva: WHO

World Health Organization (2018). HIV/AIDS: Data and statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/hiv/data/en/>